

D7.2

DAFNE+ exploitation & business plan

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Abstract

Description of current ecosystem and expected business plan of DAFNE+.

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Abbreviations

DAO	Distributed Autonomous Organization
NFT	Non Fungible Token
YOY	Year Over Year
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

1. Executive summary

This document describes the current ecosystem of NFT marketplaces in the cultural and creative industries and proposes a business plan for the DAFNE+ platform.

The deliverable presents the results of a study that combined desk research with a literature review. Concretely, the study focuses in the 11 marketplaces on the art field that have implemented or announced an intention to implement a Distributed Autonomous Organization (DAO), as DAFNE+ aims to develop a marketplace with this governance technology. Our analysis focused on marketplace activity and governance (the role of DAO and its activity), the business model implemented by the marketplaces (specifically, their key revenue sources), and the monetary value these bring to the creators. Our findings are informed by desk research using both academic and professional sources (news articles, reports, and blog articles) to account for the latest developments in the field.

The research shows the reality of NFT marketplaces, which experience strong and unpredictable changes, being a space where innovations and trends can severely affect the market capitalization. We also observe that trading activity is concentrated in the hands of a handful of professional traders, and that although many marketplaces aim to establish a DAO for their governance, only a few have actual democratic participation. Thus, there are opportunities to improve the economic and democratic participation of artists and creators in the space, although the limited benefits for creators in the ecosystem also illustrates the challenges of these technologies to realize their promises.

2. Introduction

2.1 Purpose and context of the document

This deliverable presents the activities and results of Task 7.2 during the first year of the project. More specifically, Task 7.2 studied the current ecosystem of NFT marketplaces, and, together with T6.3, researched how use case communities understand a fair economy for the cultural and creative industries in order to innovate on economic and monetization frameworks for these communities.

2.1.1 Document structure

The rest of this document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 3 describes the current NFT marketplaces' ecosystem
- Chapter 4 introduces relevant blockchain based models for the cultural and creative industries beyond NFT marketplaces.
- Chapter 5 presents the initial business plan and economic model of DAFNE+ platform
- Chapter 6 introduces the initial exploitation of results plan.
- Finally, Chapter 7 concludes this deliverable.

3. Description of existing Blockchain and NFTs platforms

This chapter describes the current ecosystem and relevant trends of NFT platforms in the creative and cultural industries.

3.1 NFT market situation and trends

While in 2022, the NFT market collapsed by 97% from \$ 17 billion in January to \$ 400 million in November 2022 (Khalili, 2022), it has returned to “life” in recent months. In Q1 2023, there has been an increase in trading volume (\$4.7 billion), and the number of unique active wallets (unique traders) has been growing since 2022, although the pace has been slowing down in recent months (Gherghelas, 2022, 2023). In Q2 2023, the NFT market activity has been slowing down considerably, with a 30% decline in trading volume in April 2023 (Rustgi, 2023).

In the art and collectibles field, the growth has been driven mainly by two marketplaces: OpenSea and Blur. Blur - a platform launched in October 2022 and positioning itself as an “NFT Marketplace for Pro Traders” - accounted for 70.5% of the market trading volume in Q1, overcoming the long-standing market leader OpenSea (Gherghelas, 2023). An analysis of Blur’s success factors and the business model suggests that their rapid growth was driven by a focus on a specific target audience – professional traders - rather than creators, retail customers or art collectors that used to be the focus of most NFT marketplaces (Santillana Linares, 2023). In fact, analysts suggest that the “revival” in the NFT market in Q1 2023 was driven by the Blur token airdrop in February 2023, which lured “airdrop hunters” to the marketplace and incentivised trading (Rustgi, 2023). Although the launch of Blur.io may have positively affected the NFT

market activity, its effect on the digital creative economy has been controversial due to its no-royalty policy (see “Royalties” in the “Creator value” section).

NFT marketplaces have also been struggling with challenges such as attempts to manipulate the market by actors buying their own assets (wash trading), and fake and plagiarised art. For example, about 95% of all trading volume on LooksRare has been attributed to wash trading (Chainalysis Team, 2022; Sergeenkov, 2022a), while about 80% of the NFTs minted on OpenSea were of plagiarised or fake works and spam, according to an analysis conducted by OpenSea itself (Pearson, 2022).

These trends suggest that the activity in the NFT space is dominated by speculative trading and mostly benefits professional traders (Khalili, 2022). Most researchers or blockchain experts agree that the current use of NFTs in the art space is limited to gaining status and signalling wealth as well as technological savviness (Buterin, 2022; Frye, 2022; Kraizberg, 2023; Ravenscraft, 2022). Indeed, research shows that in 2020/2021, 75% of all NFTs were sold for less than \$15 and about 85% of all transactions were performed by the top 10 % of traders (Nadini et al., 2021). These findings suggest that the trading activity is concentrated in the hands of a handful of professional traders, and a minimal number of creators benefit from minting NFTs of their artworks, considering the minting fees that on some platforms need to be paid upfront (Chalmers et al., 2022; Ravenscraft, 2022). Moreover, research has found that artists’ ability to sell their works has been diminishing due to the growing offer and the stabilisation of demand (Vasan et al., 2022). Indeed, strong inequalities are observed between the most famous content creators and those with less reputation; and it has been observed that the relationship between collectors and creators plays an important role on the price and number of sales (Vasan et al., 2022).

3.2 DAO-driven NFT platforms

To analyse the NFT marketplace business models, we initially selected 38 marketplaces, further narrowed to 11 marketplaces that:

1. Focus on the art field.
2. Have implemented or announced an intention to implement a DAO.

These two selection criteria allowed us to focus on marketplaces that would be considered direct competitors to DAFNE+ platform with their focus on the artistic community and decentralised

governance. Thus, our analysis focused on the following platforms: Nouns, Blur, LooksRare, SuperRare, Magic Eden, Rarible, Mintable, Portion, Element, Sudoswap, and Hadeswap.

Our analysis is concentrated on marketplace activity and governance (the role of DAO and its activity), the business model implemented by the marketplaces (specifically, their key revenue sources), and the monetary value these bring to the creators. Our findings are informed by desk research using both academic and professional sources (news articles, reports, and blog articles) to account for the latest developments in the field.

We will now present an overview of the marketplace and DAO activity in the selected platforms and discuss their key revenue streams and value-creation mechanisms for the creative community.

3.2.1 Marketplace activity

In terms of marketplace activity, in general, the focal platforms conform to the downward trend observed in the NFT market: according to DappRadar data, in 7 out of 11 marketplaces, trading activity declined drastically over the past year. Platforms that displayed mostly stable trading activity are Nouns, SuperRare, Rarible, and Element.

Marketplaces that currently display the most noticeable activity (above 1000 daily users and/or transactions) are Blur, Magic Eden, Rarible, and Element. There has been a significant decrease of active users for the latter three platforms compared to May 2022 (see Table 1).

Platform	Unique active wallets (UAW)	YOY performance (UAW)	Transactions (TR)	YOY performance (TR)	% of wash trades
Blur	3.02k	n/a	5,85k	n/a	61%
Magic Eden	6,75k	-130%	871k	+109%	n/a
Rarible	2,12k	-190%	30,93k	-170%	9%
Element	2.57k	-26%	2.88k	+14%	38%
Hadeswap	217	n/a	2k	n/a	n/a
SuperRare	70	-35	120	-50%	100%
Sudoswap	24	+130%	32	+112%	100%
Nouns	6	0%	6	0%	n/a
Mintable	2	-50%	405	-50%	n/a

LooksRare	1	-199%	1	-199%	99%
Portion	0	-200%	0	-200%	n/a

Table 1: NFT marketplace performance

Notes:

- All data was sourced from DappRadar (<https://dappradar.com/>) on 22/05/2023;
- Wash trading estimate available at: <https://dune.com/hildobby/nfts-wash-trading>;
- YOY (year-over-year) performance compares the number of average users and trades for May 2023 vs. May 2022;
- No YOY data is available for Blur since the platform was launched in October 2022;
- No data for Hadeswap is available in open access; data is sourced from <https://www.hadeswap.com/>, and no YOY comparison is available.

3.2.2 DAO activity

Most platforms in our selection (10 out of 11) have adopted or are planning to adopt the ‘progressive decentralisation’ approach. First launched by a private entity or a small collective, the platforms introduced own governance tokens after a certain period and distributed these to platform users, founders, and investors. One platform in our selection – Nouns – took a different approach by starting as a DAO and launching an NFT marketplace at a later stage.

To analyse DAO activity, we focused on voting as an indicator of governance dynamics following other research in the field (e.g. Faqir-Rhazoui et al., 2021). While all platforms but one (Element) have already implemented a DAO, only three (Nouns, Hadeswap and, potentially, Magic Eden¹) had any voting activity in the past three months at time of review had no voting activity in the past year (see Table 2).

Platform	DAO proposals	DAO voters	Last activity	Source
Blur	2	57	Feb 2023	https://www.tally.xyz/gov/blur
Magic Eden	n/a	n/a	n/a	Voting on a closed Discord channel
Rarible	133	2.2k	Oct 2022	https://snapshot.org/#/rarible.eth
Element	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a

¹ Since governance proposals and voting take place on a closed discord channel accessible only to the holders of the governance token (‘Magic Ticket’ NFT), it has been impossible for us to analyse the current activity of the DAO.

Hadeswap	28	158	May 2023	https://governance.hadeswap.com/dao/HgcYAkXFT1ENpUCjBZWc1TjAAFacUwdGZRNhTHx9cuo
SuperRare	16	563	Nov 2022	https://snapshot.org/#/superraredao.eth
Sudoswap	7	122	Mar 2023	https://www.tally.xyz/gov/sudoswap
Nouns	306	48	May 2023	https://nouns.wtf/vote
Mintable	1	5	May 2022	https://snapshot.org/#/eth8888888.eth
LooksRare	0	0	n/a	https://snapshot.org/#/cryptofees.eth
Portion	6	19	May 2022	https://snapshot.org/#/portion

Table 2: DAO governance activity

SuperRare and Rarible showed the most progress in building a community to govern the DAOs (according to the number of proposals and voters), but all activity ceased by the end of 2022. Further qualitative field research would be necessary to understand the dynamics of the development of these two DAOs.

Despite comparatively low activity on the Nouns NFT marketplace, its DAO is relatively active with the highest number of proposals voted (306) and 135 proposal creators. The proposals mostly deal with the management of the treasury that contains \$50 million as of 25 May 2023 (Etherscan, 2023); DAO members vote to decide which community initiatives to fund.

3.2.3 Revenue streams

3.2.3.1 Transaction (marketplace/protocol) fees.

Currently, most platforms in our selection (10 out of 11) charge a 0-2.5% fee. The highest transaction fee (15%) is charged by SuperRare (SuperRare, 2023). While some platforms (SuperRare, LooksRare, Sudoswap and Element) deduct the fee from the sale price (i.e. the artist receives the sale amount minus the transaction fee), others charge both the buyer and the seller (e.g. Rarible - 1% for both parties, Magic Eden – a tiered fee structure with variable amounts for buyers and sellers).

While most marketplaces in our selection charge a flat fee, one platform – Magic Eden – has a tiered fee structure. Implemented as of February 2023 and currently in Beta, the model foresees five levels of fees that decrease progressively depending on users' trading activity that is calculated on a monthly basis

(Magic Eden, 2023). Both the buyer and the seller are charged fees at the point of sale; the fee amount depends on each user's respective level.

While transaction fees have been the primary revenue stream for NFT marketplaces, this changed in October 2022 with the arrival of Blur. The platform charges no transaction fees and has attracted a significant number of users, becoming the leader in the NFT field by Q1 2023 (Gherghelas, 2023). This no-commission policy has led to other platforms either significantly reducing the fees they charge (e.g. LooksRare, Magic Eden, Rarible) or foregoing them altogether (e.g. Hadeswap). This strategy, however, presents challenges to the financial sustainability of the marketplaces. Indeed, Blur is funded mainly by venture capital and it is yet to be seen if it will achieve financial sustainability in the long run (Santillana Linares, 2023).

3.2.3.2 Own tokens

Since all platforms in our selection are governed by a DAO (or there is an intention to create one), most have their own tokens that are distributed as rewards for trading or “airdropped” to active users, founders, and investors. Three out of 11 platforms (Nouns, Magic Eden and Mintable) use non-fungible ERC-721 tokens as their governance tokens to prevent speculation (cf. Mintable, 2020), while others use ERC-20 tokens.

While rewarding trading activity with a token could potentially bring an additional revenue stream to the platform and the creators, our analysis of the token price and its year-over-year change shows that this potential is currently not realised. The price of the coins stays negligible and has dropped significantly over the past year for all platforms in our selection (See Table 3).

Platform	Token	Price	Price change YOY
Blur	BLUR (ERC-20)	\$0.4817	-90%
Magic Eden	Magic Ticket (ERC-721)	n/a	n/a
Rarible	RARI (ERC-20)	\$1.27	-61%
Element	none	n/a	n/a
Hadeswap	HADES (ERC-20)	\$0.3093	-90%
SuperRare	RARE (ERC-20)	\$0.09482	-66%
Sudoswap	SUDO (ERC-20)	\$0.6284	-80
Nouns	Nouns NFT	n/a	n/a

Mintable	MINT (ERC-721)	n/a	n/a
LooksRare	LOOKS (ERC-20)	\$0.083	-83%
Portion	PRT (ERC-20)	\$0.00053509	-163%

Table 3: NFT marketplace governance tokens

Sources: Etherscan.io, DappRadar

3.2.3.3 Additional revenue streams

Some platforms – such as Mintable – propose creator promotion packages to increase the visibility of the collections. The fees collected for the service constitute an additional revenue stream.

3.2.4 Creator value

3.2.4.1 Royalties

The technology's ability to integrate royalties thus rewarding creators in perpetuity, is viewed as one of the key value drivers of NFTs for creators (Hayward, 2022a). However, royalties have been a highly contentious issue recently, and the 'royalty war' between NFT marketplaces is still ongoing (Thompson, 2023).

While the ERC-2981 royalty standard allows signalling royalty information every time an NFT is sold or re-sold (Burks et al., 2020), the royalty payment is voluntary, and its enforcement is up to the marketplaces. This lack of enforceability of royalties was used by such platforms as Sudoswap and Blur, which came up with a 0% royalty model and managed to attract a significant market share (Cryptoslav, 2023; Thompson, 2023). Indeed, while aggregating NFTs from other marketplaces that enforced royalties, these platforms offered traders a mechanism to bypass them, allowing these marketplaces to get significant traction (Thompson, 2023).

This policy also pushed other platforms like Magic Eden and LooksRare to introduce the optional royalty policy. In this case, buyers can decide whether they want to pay royalties and, if so, whether they want to pay the total amount (as set by the creator) or only part of it. This policy has led to a backlash from the creator community (Quiroz-Gutierrez, 2023; Santillana Linares, 2023). Indeed, continuously dropping the amount of royalties does result in bringing in more traders but negatively affects the creative economy (Hayward, 2022b) and has been described as a "race to the bottom" (Santillana Linares, 2023). Since then, Blur has introduced a 0,5% enforced royalty on secondary sales (Thompson, 2023).

Currently, among the 11 platforms in our selection, six platforms either have a 0-0,5% royalty policy (Blur, Sudoswap, Hadeswap, Nouns) or optional royalties (LooksRare, and Magic Eden). Only one platform (Rarible) enforces full royalties set by the creators (Rarible, 2023); another three platforms (SuperRare, Element, Mintable) enforce a maximum of 10% royalty payment.

SuperRare was the first NFT marketplace to introduce creator royalties in 2018 and pioneered collector royalties in 2021 (SuperRare, 2023). Having piloted collector royalties in 2021, the platform implemented them definitively in 2022: now, collectors get a 1% royalty after the first secondary sale, in which they are no longer a participant. The royalties they receive are reduced by 50% for each subsequent sale.

3.2.4.2 Liquidity pools

Two platforms in our selection - Sudoswap and Hadeswap – are marketplaces with Automated Market Makers (AMMs). This means that they use a mechanism to automatically sets the price of NFTs based on their current supply and demand (“bonding curve”).

On these platforms, users set up their own liquidity pools and set up a swap fee that they get from every NFT transaction. Some suggest that this model can be more beneficial to creators than the royalty model, as the artist can both be a seller and a broker in the same transaction (Jafery, 2022). However, there are currently no estimates of the benefits of the liquidity pool model for the creators.

3.2.4.3 Auctions

A relatively novel distribution method for NFT collections – daily auctions - has been adopted by Nouns DAO. Pixelated 2D avatars (“Nouns”) are generated algorithmically every 24 hours and stored directly on the Ethereum blockchain (i.e. Nouns NFTs contain an image itself rather than a link to an image stored elsewhere as is the case with most NFTs) (Marcobello & Stevens, 2022). The NFTs are then auctioned, with all the proceeds going to the DAO treasury and used to fund real-life projects and community initiatives (Marcobello & Stevens, 2022; NFT Evening, 2022b). The project initiators receive every 10th Noun as a reward. Apart from the daily auctions, the Nouns Marketplace allows secondary trades of Nouns and extension projects’ NFTs and charges a 0% transaction fee. This model foregoes royalties but allows for a steady source of income for the community and a way to raise funds for community initiatives. As of 25 May 2023, Nouns DAO treasury amounts to \$50 million (Etherscan, 2023).

Portion.io, launched in 2018, is another project using the auction model. The focus is on high-end, luxury audiences, and the value proposition is to “provide a transparent and trusted means to track provenance and exchange authentic, high-value goods in exchange for cryptocurrency” (Portion, 2020, p. 3). The platform has a stringent authentication process to establish the provenance of digital artworks (VentureBeat, 2018) and focuses on both digital and physical art. The auction house claimed to transfer 100% of the sales proceeds to the artist (Decentraland, 2021). The platform also made a move to create a DAO launching its own PRT token and established itself in the metaverse with a virtual museum and exhibition space with a \$1.2 million virtual plot purchase (Decentraland, 2021; NFT Evening, 2022a). However, the analysis of historical activity on the marketplace by DappRadar, shows almost no trading since July 2021. The social media accounts and the blog also do not indicate any activity since 2021, which raises questions about the project’s viability.

3.2.4.4 Protocol fee sharing model.

LooksRare is the only platform in our selection to have implemented the protocol fee-sharing model. Having made royalties optional in October 2022, the platform devised an alternative way to support the creator community and announced that it would direct 25% of its protocol fee (marketplace/transaction fees) to creators (Hayward, 2022c). At the same time, the marketplace has recently dropped the protocol fee from 2% to 0.5% (LooksRare, 2023), potentially leading to lower gains for the creators. Currently, there are no estimates of this model’s benefits for creators.

3.3 Governance

Our analysis has shown a minimal number of successful cases of progressive decentralisation and community building via DAOs. Nouns DAO is one of the best examples of fundraising for the creative community and collective treasury management with a considerable number of proposals and an engaged community. However, as the NFTs traded on the marketplace are algorithmically generated, it is not necessarily an example of how an artistic community can capture value from their creations. On the other hand, our findings may suggest that although the community is recognised as an essential factor by many platforms, the “marketplace first, community second” approach has limitations. It may be challenging to build a community if it is not part of the platform development from the outset.

Recent research suggests that a better understanding and design of DAO governance could be achieved by drawing upon similar models such as cooperatives, or, more specifically, platform cooperatives (cf. Nabben et al., 2021). Platform cooperatives are digital platforms that are collectively owned and governed by their users or other stakeholders (Schneider, 2018; Scholz, 2016).

Indeed, it has been suggested that DAOs and platform cooperatives are similar in their aims of democratic ownership, governance, economic participation, cooperation and concern for the community among others (cf. Mannan, 2018; Nabben et al., 2021)

While the platform cooperative movement is gaining traction, both platform and traditional cooperatives as well as DAOs face similar issues, such as limited potential for scalability, lack of transparency and accountability, difficulty in ensuring democratic governance, low member involvement in large cooperatives, ineffective collective decision-making and lack of funding (see Nabben et al., 2021 for a review).

Research suggests that one of the crucial aspects for DAOs is the alignment between participant ownership, contributions and benefit as well as the design of incentives to govern the relationships within DAOs and between them (Nabben et al., 2021; Voshmgir, 2020). Further research is needed, however, into the best practices in the design of the incentives and governance mechanisms within cooperatives and DAOs. Such research could focus on some of the key dimensions of democratic design decisions revolving around the nature of work and value creation, data ownership, intellectual property, protocols, finance, education and training, governance and policy (Schneider, 2018).

4. Blockchain based business models for the Creative and Cultural Industries

Previous research has classified blockchain-based business models into five categories: blockchain for business integration (improving interoperability among users), blockchain as multisided platform (provision of a marketplace without intermediaries), blockchain for security (reinforcement of security assets), blockchain technology as offering (provision of blockchain APIs), and blockchain as monetary value transfer (direct value transfer among peers) (Weking et al., 2020).

Our analysis of the NFT marketplaces suggest that most could be classified as multisided platform type of business model. However, the promise of decentralisation and disintermediation brought by blockchain is not yet fully realised in most of them since most platforms are not completely decentralised (also see the “Governance” section below). Moreover, some platforms such as Sudoswap and Hadeswap could fall into the last category (blockchain as monetary value transfer) by enabling direct peer-to-peer exchanges via liquidity pools.

The analysis of the NFT marketplaces in our selection showed that some of the most common revenue streams are marketplace fees and own tokens. However, with intense competition in the space and the rise of platforms charging no commission (and having no other funding sources than venture capital), the marketplace fees have been driven down for most platforms in our selection. Their long-term viability remains to be seen.

With respect to own tokens, most platforms adopted ERC-20 tokens for governance and distributed them through airdrops or as rewards for trading activity. However, our analysis shows that this is not a reliable revenue stream, given that the token price has dropped considerably (60-90%) over the past year for all platforms in our selection.

Regarding value streams to creators, we have identified several approaches, such as royalties, liquidity pools, auctions, and the protocol fee-sharing model. As the competition between the marketplaces intensifies, so does the ‘royalty war’ and many platforms have been cutting down royalty payments or introducing optional royalties. This has led to a backlash from the creator community, and the NFT space has yet to solve the royalty dilemma.

While some alternative models have appeared, such as the liquidity pool and the protocol fee-sharing model, currently, there are no estimates or comparisons of the relative advantages of these models for creators. Additional quantitative research is necessary to analyse raw transaction data and evaluate the benefit of these models for the creators.

While NFTs may promise to solve some long-standing challenges in the digital art field – such as proof of ownership, verifiability and the ability for creators to earn fair compensation for their artworks – to date, the debate remains whether this technology can keep its promises (Chalmers et al., 2022) and whether NFTs have value and utility for the creator community (Gherghelas, 2023; Santillana Linares, 2023).

4.1 Alternatives to traditional NFTs

Several potential development paths for the NFT technology that can improve its utility for the creator community have been proposed, such as dynamic NFTs, utility NFTs, and non-transferable NFTs.

The concept of *dynamic NFTs* refers to NFTs that change over time – after they have been minted – based on external conditions or stimuli, thus creating ‘living art’ (Chalmers et al., 2022; Sergeenkov, 2023). While the concept is not novel and has been used since 2018 by such projects as Cryptokitties, it has been suggested that the full potential of dynamic NFTs is yet to be explored by artists and could enable them to tap into new, non-traditional revenue streams (Chalmers et al., 2022).

Moreover, *utility NFTs* – granting specific privileges to holders, such as access to specific communities, events, services or software – are expected to gain more importance in the near future (Gherghelas, 2022). Such NFTs could “recast [the NFT technology] in a different light and facilitate community-building” (Khalili, 2022).

Non-transferable or “soulbound” NFTs – have been proposed by Buterin (2022) and Weyl et al. (2022) as a means to move away from the “hyper-financialisation” of the crypto sphere, reduce reliance on central entities and discourage the use of NFTs as ‘status symbols’. The concept is still being researched, and its use cases are not well identified. Some examples relevant to the creative industry can include reputation-based voting for DAOs, storing achievements and credentials (which could help address the issue of fake and plagiarised art by means of introducing verified artist credentials), or verifying attendance to an event (Sergeenkov, 2022b).

Additionally, the use of NFTs has been proposed for alternative and innovative creative content, such as interactive or generative art, meaning art that is algorithmically created, with different parameters generating different pieces. Indeed, NFTs offer a promising technology to enable the monetization of interactive or generative art, where collectors could “mint” unique and customized art pieces. Some of the marketplaces that offer this alternative content are fxhash, Grailers or Async Art. DAFNE+ will explore the use of NFTs for new types of creative and cultural content.

Next, we offer an overview of the proposals exploring this use of NFTs for alternative types of content.

4.2 Blockchain-Based models for funding and value distribution

In addition to what we can observe in the field of NFTs, DAFNE+ can take inspiration from the use of blockchain technology and DAOs for the management and distribution of value. We introduce some of these applications, including Collective Fund Management, Crowdfunding or Recognition of contributions.

4.2.1 DAOs for Collective Fund Management

DAOs are blockchain-based digital organizations where participants collectively manage crypto-currency funds. These organizations can implement different governance mechanisms, although the most basic model uses tokens as a way to represent shares in these organizations, giving token-holders governance and economic rights in the organization that are proportional to the number of tokens they own. NFT marketplaces often use (or promise to use in the future) a DAO where community members can decide the rules of the marketplace and can profit from the economic benefits of the platform.

4.2.2 Crowdfunding and patronage

Blockchain technologies have enabled new forms of collective funding. DAOs were introduced as open and autonomous companies, where people could invest and take part in the decisions. Similarly, blockchain can facilitate the acquisition of donations and funds for organizations without a commercial purpose. This is the case of [Giveth](#) for non-profit causes, or the much larger [Gitcoin](#), that have obtained over \$50 million in donations, distributing grants for Open Source projects valued by their communities. Gitcoin's "quadratic funding" strategy combines strong incentives for community participation (making it much more profitable to obtain donations from multiple distinct people than to obtain big donations) with the support of external sponsors that match the received donations.

4.2.3 Recognition of contributions and distribution of profit

Many have seen the opportunities of Blockchain for automatic distribution of revenue and profits. Similarly to how DAOs can distribute their value to their token holders, these organizations can distribute their value among those who have contributed to their development, purpose, and activities. Some of the projects exploring this distribution of profits to contributors are [SourceCred](#), a project to automatically distribute tokens to community owners based on their online participation; [Commons Stack](#), that enables community members to "praise" the contributions of other members with tokens

recognizing their work, or [Hypercerts](#), where people can obtain tokens for their contributions to positive impact projects.

In addition to what we can observe in the field of NFTs, DAFNE+ can take inspiration from the use of blockchain technology and DAOs for the management and distribution of value.

5. DAFNE+ Initial Business plan

This section introduces the proposal of the initial economic model of the DAFNE+ platform. The proposal is informed by the insights and learnings from our research on NFT marketplaces and the research performed with the use cases communities. This initial proposal will be the basis for other innovative economic and governance models, that will be explored with the communities in the following phases of the project.

5.1 Business Plan

Currently, the NFT marketplace ecosystem offers few benefits for artists, as the fees and royalties have radically dropped, and the benefits seem to be concentrated in professional trading and speculation rather than with creators. Moreover, the promises of community governance have not been realized, leaving creators disempowered in the decision-making and value distribution.

DAFNE+ proposes a business model that aims to revert these trends, empowering creators. Our platform will consist of an NFT marketplace where creators will sell their content. Additionally, DAFNE+ users will democratically decide on how these fees will be distributed. Concretely, they can make and vote proposals to decide where to expend the resources of the platform's DAO.

5.1.1 A Fair and Democratic NFT marketplace

Following our findings in research with use case communities performed in WP6, the platform will implement progressive fees, requiring a higher percentage to the more expensive transactions, and establishing small fees for cheaper ones. This proposal has not been explored in the NFT space; indeed, some marketplaces reduce fees for those making more transactions (Magic Eden). However, this proposal might attract creators and collectors looking for a fair marketplace, a marketplace where creators can decide how these fees will be expended.

Thus, the platform will consist of 1) an NFT Marketplace 2) with a progressive fees structure, and 3) a DAO for economic democracy.

These are described in more detail below:

5.1.1.1 NFT Marketplace

One of the key functionalities of the platform is the NFT marketplace. In this marketplace, the content creators will be able to sell a wide diversity of content and software. The DAFNE+ project will enable creators to choose and sell under different licenses for their content. This focus on licensing will be another unique value proposition of our platform, that will offer flexibility and legally sound ways to trade content, and allow the management of the intellectual property rights of creators.

To distribute the NFT prices among the different creators, DAFNE+ will enable the self-declaration of participation, where the user listing the NFT will tell the percentage of participation of each of the other contributors. This way, the earnings can be automatically distributed among all contributors. Alternative models to explore in the future include using automatic recognition of contributions to calculate rewards for each artist (similar to SourceCred), including social recognition systems of rewards like praise, that allow the community to thank and reward any contributor, or using DAOs to calculate revenue sharing and participation ([sudswap](#), [Commons Stack](#), [SPECRTE](#)).

5.1.1.2 Redistribution and Fees

NFT marketplaces charge a fee for each NFT transaction. As introduced before, the finding that our communities want to explore “taxation” and “redistribution” as the means to create a fairer economy for the Cultural and Creative Industries, encourage the exploration and experimentation of redistributive economic models.

Thus, DAFNE+ will implement a fee structure that will depend on the value of the transactions, ranging from 0.1% to 10%. Larger transactions and wealthier actors will be expected to contribute bigger fees. Later, these fees will be used to maintain the infrastructure and support the community initiatives using the DAO governance, as explained in next section.

5.1.1.3 DAO for economic democracy

The third component of the economic model of DAFNE+ platform is a DAO. In this DAO, users will decide on economic and governance models they want to adopt for their communities, as well as propose how to expend the resources of the DAO and vote such proposals.

Our research shows us that the only active DAOs in the NFT marketplaces space are those that collectively manage funds. Our platform will thus implement such DAO where the users perceive that their votes can be translated into actual economic support for their projects and proposals.

The users will be able to decide how the DAO resources are expended to maintain and develop the platform (internal funding), as well as propose independent projects and community initiatives to support. Additionally, the platform will host prizes contests where the community can decide the winners. The platform will offer a chat, forum, and blockchain-enabled voting for this purpose. The details on how this proposals, discussion and voting will be implemented are described in detail in D2.2.

The DAO will host two types of decisions: 1) democratic decisions where each member has a vote for things such as deciding the rules of the DAO, or the decisions affecting the platform. and 2) funding decisions, where users will be able to support with their tokens economic decisions to fund specific proposals.

5.1.2 Unique value propositions

The structure of the basic economic model and business plan for DAFNE+ platform will be supported by our unique value propositions, that each of the use cases will develop and implement (See D2.2 for a detailed description of the use cases specification).

5.1.2.1 Fairness

The fairness and democracy of our platform is one of the key selling points, as well as one of the objectives of the project. Thus, we should be able to attract and inspire users that are looking for such a fair platform.

5.1.2.2 Licensing

Users will be able to offer a diversity of licenses for the content they add to the platform. This innovation will enable new uses of blockchain and NFT technologies, using them as the means to grant licenses in a more agile and personalized manner.

5.1.2.3 New types of content

The use of NFTs for new types of content is another key characteristic of our platform. The project will enable new types of content shared and sold as NFTs, such as designs and objects of digital fabrication or generative art. There are projects such as INTERFACER that have already explored the use of NFTs and digital ledgers for digital fabrication, and NFT platforms such as fxhash, Grailers or Async Art that are specialized in generative art. DAFNE+ will build on top of these, and expand the possibilities of blockchain technologies for these content types.

5.1.2.4 Collector and Creator relationship

The relationship with collectors is key for creators in order to have a more sustainable and bigger source of income. This has also been observed in the NFT space. Thus, DAFNE+ will explore ways to build and facilitate these relationships, offering functionalities similar to Patreon, where creators can give access to exclusive content or perks for the people that support their projects. This can be implemented with utility tokens giving access to premiers, or even soul-bound tokens to reflect that a person was one of the first supporters of an artist.

6. Exploitation of Results

6.1 Exploitation strategy

The results of DAFNE+ in the form of software, knowledge, designs, data, and other resources will be managed to optimize their impact. Moreover, our strategy will reflect the values of openness, fairness, and democracy that the project advocates for. Thus, we will prioritize Open licenses, both for the source code of the software projects and for any other content such as research papers or designs.

Additionally, the exploitation strategy should work together with the business plan. For this, we will organize regular workshops to refine the Business Model of each meaningful DAFNE+ component

that still needs to find a sustainable business plan. In these workshops, the different partners will update their components Business Model Canvas in coordination with the most updated business plan and business model canvas of DAFNE+ project and its platform.

The sustainability of the results after the project ends depends on a sustainable strategy, that should be implemented by an organization or community. For this, we foresee the establishment of a legal figure for the stewardship of the software. Additionally, we will consider the establishment of another legal persona for the sustainable exploitation of the results, and the maintenance and development tasks. This is in line with a big part of the most successful Open Source projects such as Wikipedia (with Wikimedia Foundation as steward and Wikimedia Enterprise for the commercial exploitation) or Mozilla (with the Mozilla Foundation and Mozilla Corporation).

Moreover, the project will explore the feasibility and adequacy of sustainable models beyond traditional approaches. This includes “exit to community” and platform co-operativism strategies, were the community of users buy and own the software.

In the following section, we list the key exploitable resources, as well as the responsible partners and an overview of their planned exploitation strategy.

6.2 Key Exploitable Results

The project will produce software and knowledge results, mainly in the form of Open Source projects and Open Access academic papers. Below, we detail the main expected exploitable results.

6.2.1 Software

The project will produce several software results, from the whole platform to several components with interest on their own. The following table summarizes these components, the expected change in Technology Readiness Level (TRL), as well as drafting an exploitation plan for each of them.

Component (Partner)	Description	TRL now	TRL end	Exploitation plan
DAFNE+ Platform	The DAFNE+ Platform is a web platform acting as the	4	7-8	ENG exploitation strategy consists of exploiting this asset into the company innovation process in collaboration with the

	entry point for accessing all the features and tools provided by DAFNE+.			<p>Digital Media & Telco business unit with the aim to exploit the asset to commercialize the new technology as extension of the company offer portfolio.</p> <p>Since this asset consists of several components and features managed by ENG (and possible by other partners, in a shared way), a more detailed exploitation strategy, specific for each component, can be elaborated in a later stage.</p>
Blockchain Realm	The Blockchain Realm will consist of blockchain-ready framework able to: make simple and fast the interaction with the blockchain networks (Polygon and Ethereum)	5	8	This asset does not start from scratch but evolve an existing asset implemented by ENG. ENG exploitation strategy consists of integrating the new functionalities and improvements implemented in DAFNE+ evolution in the existing asset. In addition, this asset will be included as relevant blockchain-based cross-domain exploitation result, in the overall company innovation process in collaboration with the business unit with the aim to exploit the asset to

	<p>facilitate the deployment and integration of Smart Contracts</p> <p>provide APIs interface for blockchain core features (NFTs, Tokens, Smart Contracts methods, Monitoring...)</p>			commercialize the new technology as extension of the company offer portfolio.
Marketplace (INTRA/SYN)	The marketplace will allow for the buying and selling of any type of multimedia asset under IPR licenses.	4	6-7	INTRA and SYN will enrich their solution portfolio with blockchain-enabled marketplaces and customise/deploy them in other fields like sector specific software components (e.g. software modules for XR-based solutions for learning) and/or assets in specific sectors (like agricultural machinery).
NFT Service (INTRA/SYN)	This component allows the creation of NFT from multimedia content.	4	6-7	INTRA and SYN consider integrating this component to solutions they currently develop (e.g. for the customs solution developed by INTRA and the

				security event registration solution developed by SYN), exploiting the knowhow developed in DAFNE+.
Automatic Art Generator (SYN)	The automatic art generator can create artwork using text input from users like “impressionistic landscape”.	3	5	SYN is currently developing a set of AI-based tools and the Automatic Art Generator will be one of the components of this set to be offered to interested parties.
Style Transfer (SYN)	The style transfer tool uses images as input and produces completely new images by applying the artistic style from a reference image.	4	6	SYN is currently developing a set of AI-based tools and the Style Transfer will be one of the components of this set.
3D avatar personalization tool (CERTH)	This tool enables users to create a personalized avatar by importing face features from	3	5	CERTH as a research organization will drive the exploitation activities of the scientific findings regarding the developed tool. Thus, CERTH aims to exploit this tool through research (e.g., development of

	the users to the avatar and allowing for changes in body parameters, clothes and hair colour of the avatar.			more accurate algorithms, publications) or commercially through its spin-off companies.
3D object reconstruction tool (CERTH)	This tool transforms a set of images of a specific object captured from different angles to a 3D representation of high fidelity.	3	5	CERTH as a research organization will drive the exploitation activities of the scientific findings regarding the developed tool. Thus, CERTH aims to exploit this tool through research (e.g., development of more accurate algorithms, publications) or commercially through its spin-off companies.
3D human pose estimation tool (CERTH)	This tool transforms video sequences of humans performing actions to a 3D representation (body poses) of humans that can then be extracted to well-known	3	5	CERTH as a research organization will drive the exploitation activities of the scientific findings regarding the developed tool. Thus, CERTH aims to exploit this tool through research (e.g., development of more accurate algorithms, publications) or commercially through its spin-off companies.

	formats for usage in third-party applications.			
AI recommendation engine (CERTH)	This tool aims to recommend specific content (i.e., NFTs, tools) to the users of the DAFNE+ platform based on the user profiles.	4	6	CERTH as a research organization will drive the exploitation activities of the scientific findings regarding the developed tool. Thus, CERTH aims to exploit this tool through research (e.g., development of more accurate algorithms, publications) or commercially through its spin-off companies.
NFT content analysis tool (UPM)	Retrieve information from a NFT, the NFT could be an audio, a video, a GIF or an image, returning list of tags once analysed audio, skeleton actions, face sentiment analysis, OCR and objects	3	7	UPM as a research and educational institution, is set to launch this tool as an open-source resource. The institution intends to integrate this tool into the curricula of both master's and undergraduate students, thereby enhancing their learning experience. Furthermore, the tool will be utilized in the execution of new research projects, which may include the addition of new file types, improving detection accuracy, and generating scholarly publications. In the final phase,

				UPM will endeavor to facilitate technology transfer through the establishment of commercial spin-offs associated with the institution
Asset versioning system (IRCAM)	A system for managing successive versions of assets, both from external repositories and in a CMS	5	7	The concepts for the management of components were designed and implemented in IRCAM's Forum platform and user validation is ongoing. It extends IRCAM's Forum features and enhances the user experience. Additional designs are foreseen for the management of repositories. and will contribute to the design of the DAFNE+ related features.
Tools catalogue (IRCAM)	A user interface for browsing in the available toolset.	3	7	The extension of IRCAM's Forum API for the implementation of the DAFNE+ Tools catalogue extends IRCAM's Forum features.
RAVE V2 and greater (IRCAM)	An AI-based set of algorithms for high quality sound timbre conversion and generativity.	3-7	8	Extensions from the initial V1 algorithm were already designed and implemented. A scientific publication is being submitted. Additional research, development and production of user documentation and tutorials are foreseen. Outcomes are progressively delivered

				<p>through IRCAM's Forum, extending the available toolset, and will be also in the DAFNE+ platform It will also feed IRCAM's artistic production and training activities. The code is published open source through a non-commercial license, enabling opportunities of commercial licensing (V2 already implemented in Qosmo's Neutone free app).</p>
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6.2.2 Research & Knowledge

6.2.2.1 MMU

Planned academic outputs will centre on the relationship between DAFNE+, student communities and educational practices and outputs. We plan to produce two papers on the following topics:

- Empowering graduates to find alternative commercial models for their creative work through DAFNE+: sustaining creative communities beyond formal educational contexts and connecting to professional communities through an international DAO.
- Educational approaches to integrating blockchain and NFT tech into collaborative educational contexts, including outputs from creative events for DAFNE+ and reporting of student experience; reported value from students of smart contract supported collaboration.

The impact of these co-authored papers is expected to be in both technological and educational fields, for example informing education policy for digital technologies. These academic outputs reflect broader deliverables regarding the use DAFNE+ and the technologies it promotes for the purposes of student and alumni creative community management in higher education institutions. The development of a student-led community that supports undergraduates and graduates to

succeed within the creative economy via DAFNE+ is expected to act as a model for others in the sector.

6.2.2.2 IAAC

The exploitation plan promotes and raises awareness about the project's contents, developments, and results. This includes implementing a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy to effectively reach the Use Case 3 target audience.

The second main objective of the exploitation plan is to evaluate and improve the implementation of DAFNE+ results in practical applications. This involves assessing and including the tools and research developed for capacity building and educational activities, improving the academic program and seeking the potential implementation of expanding into other research areas or specific applicability.

Lastly, the exploitation plan strategy focuses on collaboration and network expansion by planning and harmonizing exploitation activities and events with the partners involved in the other case studies. By fostering efficient and effective communication, the aim is to extend the Use Case 3 network and create opportunities for future collaboration beyond the project's lifetime.

6.2.2.3 FCF

The research on fair economic and governance models for communities of the cultural and creative industries will result in the proposal of several innovative blockchain-based models. These models will be designed, implemented and tested within the project to contribute to the field of NFT marketplaces and blockchain. These results will be presented in academic publications and published as Open Source software.

Additionally, research will be performed along the design and development of software prototypes to understand the needs of the project's communities and discover tools that might serve them. This applied research will likely result in implemented functionalities on the platform, and will be shared as

independent results for other communities as Open Source software, as well as research papers introducing the results.

6.2.2.4 IRCAM

Impact is expected on the following dimensions of IRCAM's activities:

Knowledge production: extending state-of-the art of the technological research on audio signal processing and dissemination in publications and experimental implementations (e.g. RAVE V2-3).

Technology production: production and user test on new sound/music creative tools, with B2C licenses (IRCAM's Forum) and B2B2C licenses (third party tools).

Community management: extending/enhancing the existing features of IRCAM's Forum for the exchange of components; extending the managed assets to work directories. Experimenting new business models and community rules through DAOs. Extending the community thanks to these evolutions, including by addressing new web3 fans and collectors and members of DAFNE+'s other use-cases.

Artistic production and education: experimenting new forms of artistic production, dissemination and sponsoring through blockchains and NFTs. Benefiting from new creative tools.

7. Conclusions

Our research into the current ecosystem has shown that the NFT marketplaces have been struggling to realise their potential and bring value to the creative community. Currently most platforms mainly incentivise speculative trading and adopt a 'race to the bottom' approach by undercutting both marketplace and creator fees. Such strategies may put at stake the health of the creative ecosystem in the long run.

Thus, some of the key considerations for DAFNE+ should be how to incentivise and reward behaviours that align with the platform's values of fairness and democracy. While a variety of revenue streams –

royalties, commissions, auctions, protocol fee-sharing, liquidity pool fees – are possible, their set-up and design should be guided by the key values of the creative community and the collectors that are interested in supporting it.

However, further field research is needed to understand the perspective of creatives and collectors and their interpretation of what can be considered ‘fair’ exchanges or ‘fair’ compensation.

Moreover, additional quantitative analysis of the raw data is necessary to analyse and compare the merits of the different business models – royalties, commissions, auctions, protocol fee-sharing, liquidity pool fees – for the platforms and the creatives.

This deliverable presents the potential business models for an NFT platform that aims to support the Cultural and Creative Industries. Concretely we consider four communities within three use cases, including audio visual production, music production, digital design and fabrication, and cultural heritage content creation among others. Thus, the project does not only explore traditional NFTs but also innovative ways of using NFTs up to the point of exploring the linkage between the physical world (Digital Fabrication) and digital tokens. Such connection could enable innovation in the future circular, and data-rich economies. Additional research into the organisational and governance models implemented by some of the marketplaces in our selection – such as Rarible and SuperRare – could bring insight necessary for building a sustainable community. Moreover, looking beyond NFT marketplaces into the business models implemented by other blockchain-based projects and/or creative communities could bring insight into the potential organisational innovations that could be implemented by DAFNE+. This study of the business models for NFT marketplaces is complemented with the description of the expected Key Exploitable Resources of DAFNE+ project, and their current exploitation strategy. The project will continue its research and design activities to find sustainable economic model for the project and its components that are aligned with the values of the project and its communities.

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